

GitLab in Research Data Management

Jens Krüger*, Amir Baleghi,
Halima Saker, Simon Prikl,
Suvasini Thangaraj, Holger Gauza,
Ursula Eberhardt, Hamed Jalali,
Alexander Kirbis, Adam J. Svahn

Lucas Beuter,
Olaf Brandt

Stephan Hachinger,
Alexander Wellmann,
Johannes Munke,
Mukund Biradar

University of Tübingen
Compute Center
Wächterstraße 76
72074 Tübingen

University of Tübingen
University Library
Wilhelmstraße 32
72074 Tübingen

Leibniz Supercomputing Centre (LRZ)
Bavarian Academy of Sciences
and Humanities Garching b.M.,
Germany

Corresponding author: jens.krueger@uni-tuebingen.de

Abstract—Research Data Management (RDM) is crucial for preserving and enhancing the accessibility of research data, ensuring its findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR principles). The paper explores the implementation of a High-Availability (HA) GitLab setup for RDM, utilizing open-source solutions like Pacemaker and DRBD to ensure uninterrupted access to research resources. Additionally, we discuss the deployment of GitLab through automation tools like Ansible, simplifying the setup process and reducing the risk of errors. To address the complexity and unfamiliarity associated with GitLab to non-information scientist users, as an example, we introduce the ARCmanager, a web-based interface designed to streamline data and metadata management within GitLab repositories for the plant research community provided within the German research data management landscape. The ARCmanager aims at easing the technical barriers for researchers, enabling efficient RDM without extensive programming knowledge. With easy-to-use user interfaces and technical interfacing (e.g. to electronic lab notebook solutions) added, we aim for an optimum uptake in research collaborations.

Keywords : Research Data Management, Data Governance, GitLab infrastructure, High Availability, de.NBI

I. INTRODUCTION

Research Data Management (RDM) involves the collection of all data, tools, and processes to preserve and render research data reusable. The goal of RDM is to support researchers in their work and to make research data as open as possible with respect to findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. These aspects are the core of the FAIR principles, [1] which are increasingly recognized at the organizational level through policies imposed by research institutions and funding agencies. RDM is not an end in itself, but rather supports good scientific practice, and contributes to a high quality of scientific output. At the core of RDM are researchers and the infrastructure that supports their work. Infrastructure may include international data repositories, such as those run by the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) or EMBL's European Bioinformatics Institute (ENBL-EBI), infrastructure providers and science gateways, such as

CIPRES [2] or de.NBI [3]), and organisational structures such as university libraries. Additionally, RDM plays a crucial role in various Open Science initiatives [4], [5].

Research data can be in many formats, from textual resources to images and 3D objects. Dataset sizes may range from several MBs to many TBs. The handling of large datasets in data-intensive disciplines poses challenges to data handling and data analysis on local PCs and laptops. Typically, large datasets should be stored on centrally provided infrastructure, from which they can be transferred to analysis pipelines on HPC infrastructure using fast network connections.

RDM is commonly depicted as a cycle. The cycle starts with research planning that progresses to active research and ends with one or more research publications. The cycle may then restart through the reuse of data for another research project [6]. The requirements for descriptive metadata, such as data treatment, sample origin, pipelines used, persons involved, etc., differs between RDM stages. Importantly, this metadata is necessary to comply with the FAIR principles. RDM practices tackle challenges on the organizational and technical levels. For this paper, we focus on the technical aspects of data management in the active, data gathering stage of the research cycle, and leave organizational aspects such as RDM policies, DOI agreements, and policies on good scientific practice to the relevant institutions.

Data itself is not static. Active research involves gathering, processing and analyzing raw data, after which data may be aggregated, etc. Nonetheless, the raw data must be retained as the foundation of all subsequent work. This poses a challenge in collaborative, data-driven sciences where one dataset may address different research questions that require specialized processing. The DataPLANT consortium for fundamental plant research, funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG), developed an approach that combines the handling of data, metadata, and workflows in a defined folder and file structure. Research data are stored in Annotated Research Contexts (ARCs) that include all information to make research

data FAIR [7].

Very often, research is not a straight path to success. Instead, researchers have to be able to return to the raw data and review the history of data curation and/or processing. In complex research environments such as research groups, remote work, and international collaborations, there is a need for centralized, reliable and flexible RDM systems that retain this data history [8]. This system should serve as the central and shared data store for all researchers in a given project while being hosted on reliable infrastructure, providing minimal downtime and protection against data loss. Additionally, researchers should be in control of access to their data, whether they keep it private, share it with external collaborators, or conduct peer review. The key challenges are:

- Reliability of services supporting RDM
- Centralising of services and storage to foster accessibility
- Handling large files
- Tracking data history
- Access control to data

One standard tool that has already demonstrated its usability in the aspects mentioned above in various domains (including, e.g., neuroscience [9], [?]nodegin), is GitLab [10]. GitLab is the foundation of RDM for the large trans-regional collaborations NFDI4Plants DataHUB, [11] and PlantMicrobe (CRC/TRR 356).

GitLab is a popular, open-source, web-based version control system which can support RDM by providing a centralized platform to store, track and collaborate on research materials. It can accommodate a wide range of data formats from code and scripts to raw data files and documentation. This promotes findability, organization, and version control, ensuring everyone on the project has access to the latest versions and a clear history of changes. Ultimately, this will streamline the research workflow and foster long-term research reusability. GitLab features out-of-the-box user rights and roles that allow researchers to grant access on various levels, from read-only (reporter) for access by reviewers or data stewards, to full access (maintainer/owner) for contributing members of the research project. Researchers can clone research data from a common source, allowing a collaborative group to tackle different research questions without interfering with each other. Additionally, GitLab provides in-built mechanisms such as pipelines and webhooks to automate tasks such as quality control and the connection to external services such as publication services [11]. GitLab also features a comprehensive Application Programming Interface (API) that allows developers to create tools that mitigate GitLab complexity to help researchers focus on their scientific work.

Specifically, this paper focuses on the technical aspects of providing GitLab reliably and stable and on the challenges to overcome in supporting researchers, using the example of plant research in Germany. In this way, we want to promote GitLab not only as a tool in development but also as a valuable tool for other data-centric research disciplines.

The reference architecture supplied by GitLab [12] represents a potential solution. This implementation is impaired

by its inherent complexity, rendering it less suitable for deployment within contexts characterized by smaller user bases. Moreover, its implementation necessitates the utilization of enterprise edition features, thereby imposing constraints on accessibility. Consequently, alternative strategies are warranted to address the needs of such environments more effectively.

II. RELIABLE GITLAB

A. High-Availability

It is imperative to establish an integrated and distributed architecture to safeguard against any potential interruptions in our system [13]. Within the context of academic research, ensuring continuous progress and safeguarding valuable intellectual property requires the implementation of a High-Availability (HA) GitLab configuration accompanied by a dependable backup system. The critical importance of HA lies in its capacity to minimize downtime. Through redundant systems incorporated within an HA framework, the transition to a secondary server in the event of hardware or software failures can occur seamlessly, thereby averting outages and facilitating uninterrupted research activities [13]. Furthermore, HA serves to mitigate disruptions that could significantly impede researcher productivity. Maintaining uninterrupted access enables researchers to sustain their focus and momentum, thereby enhancing the efficiency and expediency of the research process.

HA prioritizes data integrity by replicating critical research data, code, and intellectual property across multiple servers. This minimizes the risk of data loss due to hardware failure, safeguarding the reproducibility and verifiability of research findings. This is achieved by daily incremental backups to the LRZ (Leibniz Supercomputing Centre) providing geographically dispersed, secure copies of the data, guarding against catastrophic events that might impact the de.NBI Cloud. A reliable and flexible infrastructure facilitates the seamless accommodation of growing research teams and increasingly complex collaborative research projects, fostering a robust and adaptable research environment. Implementation details of HA GitLab are illustrated in figure 1.

In essence, HA GitLab is an imperative consideration for academic institutions. It guarantees uninterrupted access to vital research resources, optimizes researcher productivity, and safeguards valuable intellectual property. The significance of HA intensifies as the number of researchers and the complexity of their projects increase.

B. Architecture Components

While the free GitLab Community Edition lacks built-in HA capability, we have implemented a robust on-premise solution using the open-source infrastructure software Pacemaker and DRBD [14] and [15]. Pacemaker, a cluster resource manager, automates failover and load balancing, ensuring minimal service disruption during server failures. DRBD, a data replication tool, synchronizes data between servers for redundancy and prevents data loss. Using free and open tools

Fig. 1. High-available GitLab Architecture with inter-region replication and LRZ Backup components in de.NBI Cloud and LRZ infrastructures in Tübingen (state 03/2024).

we maintain digital sovereignty and freedom of the scientific process.

An active-passive HA strategy was chosen to overcome limitations in controlling write operations across multiple GitLab nodes. This means one server is primary (active) and handles writes, with a secondary (passive) server ready to take over seamlessly if needed.

The backend infrastructure leverages OpenStack for compute resources and the Ceph Object Storage solution, ensuring redundancy across service, network, and storage layers.

To ensure the project’s data remains secure and accessible in the long term, our architecture utilizes Borg Backup, a data backup and synchronization platform. This system performs daily incremental backups of research data to another geographically distinct location, the LRZ (Leibniz Supercomputing Centre). These off-site copies provide a robust safeguard against catastrophic events that could potentially impact the de.NBI Cloud, since all data can be restored to the main GitLab instance once its functionality is restored.

In addition, utilizing an independent GitLab instance running on the LRZ side, a temporary mirror can be provided in case of a longer downtime of the de.NBI Cloud. This multifaceted approach establishes a highly reliable GitLab HA implementation, guaranteeing service continuity for a seamless and dependable user experience.

C. Automatic deployment

Manually setting up a highly available GitLab cluster can be cumbersome. Ensuring data consistency and high availability often involves complex tools, such as Pacemaker and DRBD. While powerful, these tools require significant expertise to

configure correctly, increasing the risk of errors. Our solution is to provide pre-configured and automatic scripts to help other institutions set up a GitLab-based research environment, utilising the Ansible automation tool [16]. By automating tasks, Ansible reduces complexity and the risk of errors associated with manual setup. Ansible can also handle the configuration of Pacemaker, DRBD with NFS services together, and other essential components like load balancers and database servers. This ensures a correctly configured and functional GitLab cluster.

D. Single sign-on and Federated Architecture

In addition to the user rights and roles, GitLab can be connected to various identity providers (IDP) such as the researcher’s home institutions, as well as meta-IDPs such as Keycloak that, in turn, enable access via, e.g., ORCID and ELIXIR AAI. Keycloak uses industry-standard protocols like OAuth 2.0 and OpenID Connect and provides a reliable and open-source framework for authentication, authorization, and token management. Tokens are handled and exchanged between services by Keycloak on behalf of the users, thus providing mechanisms for trust delegation. Additionally, Keycloak offers user-managed access. Users can edit the information shared between services and are empowered to take an active role in data protection.

III. TOOLS

RDM is necessary and valuable to scientific research, but can be complex and labour-intensive. To reduce workload, ensure data quality, and mitigate complexity, tools ensuring an efficient RDM are being provided around GitLab in our

ongoing collaborations. A large group of these tools enhance (meta-)data curation and data ingestion. Several tools of this kind have been developed by and within the DataPLANT consortium, such as Swate, ARCCommander, ARCitect, and ARCmanager [?], [17]. ARCmanager, discussed further below, is a web service that simultaneously connects to a GitLab instance and other services to streamline and simplify the process of uploading and curating datasets for researchers. Another important group of tools are those providing a secondary RDM functionality, such as Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) or Laboratory Inventory Management Systems. Below we give an example of how such tools can interoperate with GitLab to enhance RDM approaches by detailing our plan to connect the ELN software “eLabFTW” [18] to GitLab in the PlantMicrobe large collaborative project (CRC/TRR 356).

A. (Meta-)data management tools to connect to GitLab

Here, we give an overview of tools that can enhance data management, – in particular by providing easier-to-use interfaces to GitLab for RDM. Before actually elaborating on software, we recap basic requirements.

1) *Requirements on (meta-)data management tools:* Tools must reduce complexity for the researchers and simplify their workflows – this not only applies in our community, but in general. To achieve this, tools must be usable and built in a way that does not require a steep learning curve. To achieve this, a tool must provide a GUI that looks and feels like established tools. In our typical use cases, this means that tools must feel like spreadsheets. Second, tools must support compliance with relevant standards. In the case of DataPLANT, there are two relevant standards. Research data must be stored in ARCs with the appropriate files and folder structure [7]. Additionally, metadata must adhere to the ISA-Tab standard [19]. Tools should also include mechanisms to foster metadata quality. This includes the use of established research domain ontologies [20], discussed further below, instead of free text, and input validation.

2) *Swate, ARCCommander and ARCitect:* During the work within the DataPLANT consortium, the requirements and challenges mentioned above were tackled in an evolutionary approach, where each tool was succeeded by a more advanced and user-friendly tool. Most notably, the tools Swate, ARCCommander, and ARCitect form such an evolutionary chain, and the evolution continues. Swate (Swate Workflow Annotation Tool for Excel) is an Excel add-in that implements the ISA framework [19] for supplying metadata to studies and assays in the ISA.study.xlsx and ISA.assay.xlsx files. After installing Swate locally or using Swate in Excel 365, users have access to numerous metadata templates describing a variety of experimental approaches as well as ontologies [21] and [22].

ARCCommander [21] aims to reduce the necessity of learning long sequences of text commands for a Command Line Interface (CLI) by serving as a wrapper for CLI Git commands. ARCCommander simplifies user interactions, however does not remove the burden of CLI entirely.

Building on ARCCommander and Swate, ARCitect is a local application that allows users to interact with ARCs via a GUI, thus significantly simplifying the management of (meta-)data. It incorporates Swate ISA metadata and ontology collections, and utilizes the ARCtrl library to interact with locally stored ARCs and regular Git to upload and download the files and folders to the DataHUB [17].

3) *ARCmanager:* The tools mentioned above share the same caveat: they require the local installation of Git as well as the local installation of the tools themselves. This places a burden on the researcher, developers, and supporting staff to maintain cross-platform compatibility and documentation. ARCmanager is a web-based application that requires only a browser and internet connection. The primary purpose of ARCmanager is to provide an environment capable of creating and editing every aspect of the research data stored inside ARCs on GitLab. Specifically, ARCmanager was designed to edit and create new ARCs as well as to create and edit the ISA files for metadata handling within the ARC. ARCmanager is separated into frontend and backend, communicating with each other through API calls using JSON. Each of them is built using open-source frameworks, namely Vue.js for the frontend and FastAPI for the backend. Any interaction with GitLab is made through the GitLab API on the backend. Pandas, a Python library, is used to read and write to the Excel sheets for the metadata files [23], [24]. The Swate API is used to access the ontology terms and the ISA metadata templates. All read and write tasks are performed and cached at the backend side. Common tasks like uploading a file to the remote repository, adding a new user, or editing a text-based file are also possible through ARCmanager. ARCmanager leverages the potential of a centrally provided GitLab instance while reducing complexity for the researcher and simultaneously reducing complexity for supporting staff, as there is only one cross-platform tool to be maintained and documented.

B. Tools with secondary RDM functionality and GitLab – eLabFTW ELN

It is increasingly common for laboratories to work with Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs), Laboratory Inventory Management Systems, or even with tools directly uploading a data stream from instruments (e.g. imaging platforms). Such approaches to data generation and documentation must be harmonised with RDM.

In particular, the ELN software eLabFTW [18] is already used by various groups within PlantMicrobe (CRC/TRR 356). However, all significant datasets are intended to be managed within the GitLab-based RDM platform. Therefore, we envisage a data and metadata synchronisation workflow from eLabFTW to the GitLab platform of PlantMicrobe (Figure 2). This workflow starts (1) by a “controller/engine” requesting all metadata from the relevant eLabFTW instance(s). The “controller/engine” may be anything from script executed via a cron job to a system queuing complicated tasks (if functionality is extended). The request for metadata – e.g. via eLabFTW’s REST APIs – has to be implemented with

Fig. 2. Concept for interoperation of GitLab with the electronic lab notebook software eLabFTW within the CRC/TRR 356 collaboration (cf. acknowledgements). The (meta-)data transfer workflow with steps (1)-(3) is further explained in the text. The GitLab logo in this figure is subject to the MIT license (for further information, please visit <https://gitlab.com/gitlab-org/gitlab>).

sufficient rights (maintaining security), which may be a challenge. In a second step (2), the engine keeps only (meta-)data where a “publication flag” has been set by an eLabFTW user, indicating that this user considers it sensible to include the respective data in RDM. Thus, importing a deluge of insignificant, volatile, uncurated, or embargoed data can be avoided as far as needed. Lastly, the (meta-)data and any data blobs that can be obtained with it from the eLabFTW instance are formatted according to the ARC standard (3) and pushed into a sensible target repository in GitLab.

It is clear that this workflow concept still requires further elaboration, e.g. as to data access modalities and feasibility of secure implementation. However, we are confident that we can sensibly implement such a workflow at least for selected subprojects which can profit from it. Then, it can serve as a blueprint for integration of our GitLab RDM approach with similar tools (e.g. imaging platforms, etc.). The “integrated RDM” concept would represent a significant achievement, as cross-system integration efforts have proven to be challenging.

IV. DISCUSSION

GitLab, as an open-source platform for collaboration and version control envisaged for coding projects, is mainly used by programmers in the software and web development sector. People working in this area are familiar with the terminology (e.g., branch, webhook, and tag) and the concept of local and

remote repositories, as well as the concept and differences of synchronizing these repositories (e.g. the difference between *git pull* and *git fetch* as well as between *git push* and *git commit*). Scientific researchers and support staff who are not primarily engaged in software or web development are generally reluctant to undertake the significant training required to become proficient in these tools. Researchers must also trust that using RDM platforms will not result in inadvertent loss of data or public release of preliminary data. Therefore, it is necessary to mitigate complexity and unfamiliarity and to provide tools such as the ARCmanager. This approach utilizes practices and tools for software development without researchers needing to be familiar with either. Although developing and maintaining researcher-focused tools adds complexity on the technical level, doing so greatly relieves the burden on researchers.

At the same time, all the advanced interfaces natively included in GitLab instances remain in place and provide knowledgeable users the opportunity to develop solutions that are tailored to their use case. By using the GitLab API or the *git* command line interface, users are for example able to initiate bulk downloads of data from multiple repositories or retrieve all files with a specific format from a project to perform analyses with those files locally. The publicly available backend server that was developed for the ARCmanager exploits the GitLab API endpoints to provide more functionalities that are tailored to interactions with ARCs. The backend server, in turn, offers additional API endpoints to invoke all actions that can be performed through the GUI of the ARCmanager web service. Since the source code and API endpoint documentation are freely available for users, it enables those with the necessary background knowledge to take part in the further development or start developing additional services.

Git, GitLab, and GitHub target developers and are designed and optimized for line-based, textual files. This is a caveat for handling large, non-line-based binary files or files for which derivation is not easily captured as a difference between files. This applies to images, large omics datasets, and raw data that went through analytic pipelines. GitLFS mitigates these problems by handling large binary files separately. These files are only transferred if they are actually needed; otherwise, repositories only contain a pointer to these files. Thus, GitLab can be used for managing data that was not part of the initial Git development. While it is definitely true that repositories will grow substantially when working with binary files such as images for keeping track of changes, the same is true if researchers want to keep different versions without using GitLab. Research datasets tend to grow while there is still active research. This, in turn, calls for centrally provided infrastructure with enough resources and backup mechanisms in place.

Using tools that foster open research and transparency in processes requires a cultural change. While GitLab can support local repositories as well as remote repositories, the cultural shift to centrally provided infrastructure and the

acceptance of these infrastructures require establishing trust between researchers and infrastructure providers. The former must be encouraged to provide their data, while the latter must keep these data safe and protected against data loss and unwanted data sharing. Together with organizational initiatives such as policies on RDM and on open science, centralized infrastructures and tools such as GitLab are one step towards cultural change, sustainable RDM, and reusable research data.

V. OUTLOOK

GitLab provides several means to connect with other services or instances. The API and the implementation of webhooks offer enormous versatility. As demonstrated by [11], GitLab can serve as a storage backend while an external tool, InvenioRDM, in this case, serves as a DOI-based reference broker. As more and more tools, such as ELNs, are available, it might be worth elaborating on connections between services so that entries in the ELN will be transferred to a GitLab project.

Another aspect worth elaborating on is the synchronization between different GitLab instances. This might be useful in cases where institutional policies require researchers to store research data on-premise while at the same time they want to maintain a copy that can be accessed by collaborators outside the institution. In this case, synchronization between the restricted institutional GitLab instance and one of the publicly accessible GitLab implementations will do justice to the policy as well as to the need to collaborate.

Self-hosted GitLab installations offer a number of methods that can be used to replicate and synchronize a repository between two instances. The simplest solution with methods provided by the free self-hosted GitLab model is to set up push mirroring for the source repository. With this method, all changes to the source repository are automatically applied to a downstream repository, effectively creating an exact copy. The disadvantage of this method is that the downstream repository must be protected against changes from other sources, because those would lead to inconsistencies between the two copies.

It is also possible to automate the process of setting up a push mirror by using the GitLab API. Such API calls can be integrated into external applications, like the ARCmanager, to take away some of the effort of setting up push mirrors manually. The multitude of functions available through the GitLab API should even allow setting up bi-directional mirroring, a method that is normally reserved for the premium version of GitLab. Bi-directional mirroring replicates changes of both repositories to its counterpart, which creates additional difficulties that need to be taken into account when developing such a solution. Which of these solutions for synchronization between repositories on two different GitLab instances will be implemented needs to be determined in discussions with the user base and other stakeholders.

The rich APIs of GitLab and of modern laboratory applications with RDM functionality - such as ELNs - can probably be leveraged to integrate these applications with our GitLab-based

RDM approach. We plan to test this with the ELN software eLabFTW and one of our GitLab instances.

VI. CONCLUSION

RDM is a challenge for researchers as well as for supporting infrastructure. It is not a mere technical task but rather a cultural change that must be carried out by a reliable infrastructure as well as by designated tools. In this paper we highlight GitLab and associated approaches as the base for RDM and data handling. Second, we demonstrate how a reliable HA infrastructure can be built and deployed using open-source components. Finally, we indicate the need for tools to make things as easy as possible for researchers and supporting staff alike. In essence, we have endeavoured to describe how to provide a reliable GitLab-based infrastructure and why you should do it.

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